

Mechanistic studies on the chlorination of phenols with *N*-chlorobenzene sulphonamide

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The effects of substituents on the kinetics and reaction mechanism of chlorination of twenty three *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-substituted phenols by *N*-chlorobenzenesulphonamide (CAB) are reported. The variable order dependence on the substrate concentration for the substituents can be described by the rate equation,

$$-d[\text{CAB}]/dt = k'[\text{Ph}][\text{CAB}][\text{H}^+] + k''[\text{H}_2\text{O}][\text{CAB}][\text{H}^+]^2.$$

The reaction is acid catalysed and its dependence on H_0 function suggests the presence of water molecule as a nucleophile in the rate-limiting step. The concave Hammett plot shows a transition in the rate-limiting step with varying nature of the substituents. The linear relation in the Exner plot suggests the operation of a similar mechanism in all the substituted phenols.

Phenol, a widely used industrial chemical, is known to induce systemic injuries, fatalities in animals and human beings. It has shown exceptional qualities as a bactericide. Phenols and its compounds are commonly found as dilute contaminants in groundwater and surface water^{1,2}. Chlorophenols, the products of phenolic chlorination, have considerable potential as intermediates in the synthesis of organic compounds³.

Yeddanapalli and Gnanapragasam studied the kinetics of bromination of phenol⁴ by IBr in glacial acetic acid. The following scheme is proposed for the mechanism of bromination of phenol.

In contrast to facile bromination, chlorination of phenols with CAB is too slow to measure. Studies of bromination of phenol with *N*-bromosuccinimide and 2,4,4,6-tetrabromocyclohexa-2,5-dienone⁵ reveal that both reagents brominate phenol by a different mechanism from that of molecular bromine. Acid catalysed chlorination of phenols by aqueous HOCl has been investigated⁶⁻⁸. Substituents on the aromatic ring in phenol can influence the nucleophilicity and nucleofugality by changing its acidity⁹. We now report the chlorination of twenty three mono substituted

phenols in aqueous acetic acid medium as well as the effect of the substituents. The structure-reactivity relationships are ascertained by the application of linear free-energy relationships.

Results and discussion

First order dependence on [CAB] was evidenced by the linear semilogarithmic plots of titre versus time ($r \approx 0.998$; $s \approx 0.012$). Slight decomposition of the oxidant is observed under the highly acidic experimental conditions maintained. The true pseudo-first order rate constants are calculated using the relation, $k_{\text{cal}} = k_{\text{obs}} - k_{\text{decomp}}$ ($k_{\text{decomp}} = 0.281 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $[\text{CAB}] = 2.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.46 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{AcOH} : \text{H}_2\text{O} = 60 : 40$ at 313 K).

The order dependence on [phenol] is zero (Table 1). The kinetics was examined at different initial concentrations of HClO_4 , ranging from 0.94 to 2.03 mol dm^{-3} . The reactivity increases with increasing acidity as shown in Table 1. No levelling of rate constants takes place at higher acidities. Hammett's acidity function H_0 is used as a measure of the acidity of the medium since fairly high acid concentrations are maintained in the reaction. The values¹⁰ of H_0 have been taken from the literature. The Zucker-Hammett plot (Fig. 1) is fairly linear ($r = 0.995$; $s = 0.039$) with a slope of 1.7. In the plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [\text{H}^+]$ the correlation is relatively poor as expected¹¹ ($r = 0.988$; $s = 0.062$).

Table 2 shows that the insensitivity of added acrylonitrile rules out a mechanism involving a free radical process. Change in ionic strength has a marked effect on the reactivity. Significant influence of $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$ on the

Table 1. Effect of reactants on the rate of oxidation of phenols at 313 K in aqueous acetic acid medium

Solvent AcOH : water = 60 : 40 (v/v)			
10^3 [CAB] mol dm ⁻³	10^2 [PhOH] mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{cal}$ s ⁻¹
1.42	4.45	1.46	2.43
2.02	4.45	1.46	2.47
3.04	4.45	1.46	2.54
4.05	4.45	1.46	2.52
2.02	2.25	1.46	2.43
2.02	4.45	1.46	2.47
2.02	6.68	1.46	2.48
2.02	11.25	1.46	2.40
2.02	15.75	1.46	2.28
2.02	20.75	1.46	2.41
2.02	27.00	1.46	2.29
2.02	4.45	0.94	0.80
2.02	4.45	1.18	1.10
2.02	4.45	1.46	2.47
2.02	4.45	1.60	2.89
2.02	4.45	1.79	4.70
2.02	4.45	2.03	7.05

Fig. 1. Zucker-Hammett plot.

reactivity is exhibited. The kinetic results are summarised in Table 2. Dielectric changes have a marked effect and the reactivity of phenols increases as the amount of acetic acid in the solvent is increased (Table 3). This is quite likely due to the increase in the $-H_0$ values of the reaction mixture^{12,13}. Linear plot of $\log k_{cal}$ versus D^{-1} ($r = 0.990$; $s = 0.080$) with a positive slope very much suggests that there is an involvement of positive ion in the rate-limiting step. D₂O slightly increases the rate of conversion of phenols. A solvent isotope effect on rate is related to solvation effects in the two solvents¹⁴.

Table 2. Effect of acrylonitrile, sodium perchlorate and chloride ion on the reaction rate at 313 K

Solvent AcOH : water = 60 : 40 (v/v), [CAB] = 2.02×10^{-3} mol dm ⁻³ , [PhOH] = 4.45×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , [HClO ₄] = 1.46 mol dm ⁻³			
10^4 [Acrylonitrile] mol dm ⁻³	10^3 [NaClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	10^4 [NaCl] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{cal}$ s ⁻¹
0.00	—	—	2.47
2.40	—	—	2.27
4.83	—	—	2.37
7.20	—	—	2.36
14.40	—	—	2.40
—	2.80	—	4.74
—	4.50	—	6.23
—	7.00	—	9.42
—	14.00	—	15.15
—	—	1.00	7.26
—	—	—	(5.49)
—	—	1.50	10.34
—	—	—	(7.12)
—	—	2.00	13.36
—	—	—	(9.65)
—	—	3.00	21.12
—	—	—	(15.29)

The values in parentheses are rate coefficients representing the effect of KBr on the reactivity.

Table 3. Solvent effect

[CAB] = 2.02×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [PhOH] = 4.45×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 1.46 mol dm⁻³

D^0	Solvent % AcOH : H ₂ O : D ₂ O	$10^4 k_{cal}$ s ⁻¹
49.60	—	0.81
42.37	—	1.07
35.14	—	2.47
27.90	—	4.68
20.67	—	14.28
—	60 : 37.50 : 2.50	2.38
—	60 : 27.50 : 12.50	2.57
—	60 : 20.00 : 20.00	3.24

^aDielectric constant values are calculated from the values of the pure solvents.

Substituent effects :

Substituent effects are used to probe the reaction mechanism since the reactivity of aromatic compounds can be affected by electronic nature of the substituents. The effect of substituents on the reactivity has been investigated by employing twenty three *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-substituted

Table 4. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of phenols with CAB in aqueous acetic acid medium 313 K
Solvent AcOH : water = 60 : 40 (v/v), [CAB] = 2.02×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [PhOH] = 4.45×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 1.46 mol dm⁻³

SL. no.	Phenols	$10^4 k_{\text{cal}}/s^{-1}$			ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>
		30°	40°	50°	kJ mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹		
1.	H	0.97	2.47	5.05	64.5	109.0	98.6	0.998	0.071
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	1.46	3.03	6.71	59.5	122.5	97.8	0.999	0.050
3.	<i>p</i> - <i>t</i> -Butyl	1.10	2.04	4.84	57.8	130.7	98.7	0.993	0.115
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	0.79	1.85	4.34	66.8	103.2	99.2	0.999	0.107
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	0.75	1.76	4.01	66.1	106.3	99.3	0.999	0.003
6.	<i>p</i> -COCH ₃	0.38	1.24	3.60	89.3	35.0	100.3	0.999	0.026
7.	<i>p</i> -COOH	0.86	2.25	4.52	69.4	94.0	98.8	0.999	0.053
8.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.64	1.70	3.85	70.6	92.4	99.5	0.999	0.048
9.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	2.32	4.56	11.80	63.5	105.7	96.6	0.993	0.133
10.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	12.74	22.08	38.76	42.8	159.5	92.7	0.999	0.016
11.	<i>m</i> -Cl	0.80	1.72	3.31	55.5	140.4	99.4	0.999	0.032
12.	<i>m</i> -OH	26.22	45.53	88.66	47.2	138.9	90.7	0.997	0.063
13.	<i>m</i> -NH ₂	1.45	3.70	6.49	58.4	125.4	97.7	0.991	0.134
14.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.66	1.89	3.14	67.8	101.0	99.4	0.994	0.135
15.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	0.82	1.99	4.89	70.1	92.2	99.0	0.999	0.029
16.	<i>o</i> - <i>t</i> -Butyl	1.19	3.60	7.75	73.9	76.0	97.7	0.996	0.113
17.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	1.01	2.39	6.32	72.1	83.9	98.4	0.999	0.066
18.	<i>o</i> -Cl	0.69	1.37	3.39	62.3	119.7	99.7	0.995	0.104
19.	<i>o</i> -Br	0.54	1.54	4.26	81.5	57.8	99.6	0.999	0.007
20.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.37	1.13	3.37	87.6	40.8	106.3	0.999	0.014
21.	<i>o</i> -CHO	0.34	1.20	4.00	97.8	7.8	100.3	0.999	0.004
22.	<i>o</i> -COOH	0.55	1.28	4.19	79.8	64.1	99.8	0.993	0.162
23.	<i>o</i> -COOCH ₃	0.56	1.40	3.69	74.2	82.02	99.8	0.999	0.046

phenols. Prima facie, the results suggest that electron-releasing substituents accelerate the rate while the electron-withdrawing ones retard the reactivity (Table 4). In *ortho*-substituted compounds, in addition to inductive and resonance effects, 'proximity effect' also plays a role in the reactivity. The rate coefficients and activation parameters are evaluated from the plots of $\ln k_{\text{cal}}/T$ versus $1/T$. A scan of Table 4 reveals that the substituent effects in this reaction system are small (barring *m*-OCH₃ and *m*-OH) which is in consonance with the observation of nearly zero order dependence on [substrate].

Individual orders with respect to the concentration of the substrates are determined for all the substituents by the 'method of integration' and given in Table 5. The varying order with various phenols has also been noticed in the bromination of phenols by *N*-bromosuccinimide¹⁵ and in the chlorination of phenols by chloramine-T¹⁶. It seems that the order in the substrate is not a function of the position of the substituent. Product analysis shows that all the listed phenols give only monochlorinated products. In the bro-

mination of phenols¹⁷ by PyHBr₃ as far as *p*-isomers are considered, direct attack by PyHBr₃ at the *ortho*-position may suffer steric hindrance due to the presence of nearby -OH group. It was suggested that relatively smaller species Br₂ would be the effective electrophile. In the present investigation, similar arguments will support the involvement of Cl₂ in the reaction sequence as the effective electrophile. Anyway, the clean first order kinetics with respect to [CAB] is not in support of this view. Other possible reaction species are RNHCl, RNH₂Cl⁺, HOCl and H₂OCl⁺ under the acidic conditions maintained.

Variable order dependence on [substrate] with respect to the substituents can be associated with mechanistic changes. But, an explanation based on change in reaction mechanism is ruled out in the present study for the following reasons :

- (i) Near constancy in ΔG^\ddagger values (Table 4).
- (ii) There is not much of deviation in the isokinetic plot ($r = 0.988$; $s = 1.992$).

Table 5. Order dependence on [substrate]

Sl. no.	Substrate	Order in [substrate]
1.	H	0.00
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	0.00
3.	<i>p</i> - <i>t</i> .Butyl	0.00
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	0.00
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	0.50
6.	<i>p</i> -COCH ₃	0.26
7.	<i>p</i> -COOH	0.49
8.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.00
9.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	0.71
10.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	0.93
11.	<i>m</i> -Cl	0.32
12.	<i>m</i> -OH	0.73
13.	<i>m</i> -NH ₂	0.25
14.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.50
15.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	0.38
16.	<i>o</i> - <i>t</i> .Butyl	0.55
17.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	0.29
18.	<i>o</i> -Cl	0.00
19.	<i>o</i> -Br	0.00
20.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	1.50
21.	<i>o</i> -CHO	0.00
22.	<i>o</i> -COOH	0.00
23.	<i>o</i> -COOCH ₃	0.00

(iii) Exner plot is linear with an excellent correlation coefficient (Fig. 2), ($r = 0.990$; $s = 0.058$).

(iv) Change in reaction mechanism would require the oxidant to be ambiphilic in contrast with the experimental observations.

All these observations very much favour an operation of similar mechanism in the oxidation of all the listed phenols.

Fig. 2. The Exner plot (numbered as in Table 4).

Hammett correlations have been employed to understand the reaction mechanism involved in the chlorination of phenols. An examination of Fig. 3 reveals an indefinite linear relationship. It seems that all the *meta*- and *para*-substituents, excluding the *m*-OCH₃ and *m*-OH groups, fall on a concave Hammett curve. Reports of -OCH₃ group deviation are very common in literature^{18,19}. Hydroxyl, attached to an unsaturated system is very powerfully electron releasing²⁰; in certain circumstances it seems even more so than methoxyl. Hammett σ values are based on ionization of benzoic acid in water at 25°C. In benzoic acid 'through conjugation' is missing and as such σ values will not serve the purpose here. Simply, in the case of *m*-OCH₃ and *m*-OH substituents the magnitude of the change is not related to Hammett's σ values. Instead of the Hammett σ value, if $\sigma_R^{(BA)}$ value (-0.61) is used, then the *m*-OCH₃ substituent also falls on the curve (Fig. 3). Also, electronic behaviour of -OH depends on the solvent. It is often not easy to interpret results for *m*-OH. Hence *m*-OH is not taken into consideration in establishing the Hammett line. Brown-Okamoto relation do not improve the situation. The $\rho\sigma^-$ plot also shows a high degree of scatter.

Fig. 3 shows a well defined break that demonstrates a change in the nature of the rate-determining step with the nature of the substituent. The ρ values corresponding to the two branches of the curve are -1.77 and -0.42 (30°) respec-

Fig. 3. The Hammett plot (σ_R^{BA} value is used for *m*-OCH₃; *m*-OH is not included in the correlation; + using σ value for *m*-OCH₃) (numbered as in Table 4).

tively. Negative ρ values very much imply the cationic character in the transition state. A type of transition state with a fully developed positive charge on the phenyl ring is quite unlikely in view of low magnitude of ρ values. The ρ values corresponding to the two limbs of the curve are listed

in Table 6.

Temp. (°C)	ρ -	ρ -
30	1.74	0.42
40	1.50	0.29
50	1.43	0.30

Attempts have been made to express the kinetic data in terms of Yukawa-Tsuno equation²¹ (i), taking into account an exalted resonance contribution.

$$\log(k/k_0) = \rho(\sigma + r^+ \Delta\sigma_R^+) \quad (i)$$

where r^+ is a constant depending on the resonance effect in the reaction and $\Delta\sigma_R^+$ measures the capacities of substituents to supply electrons by resonance. As is clear from Fig. 4, the correlation does not improve much ($r = 0.674$; $s = 0.106$) and the equation fails to explain the reactivity. The effect of *para*-substituents on the first-order rate coefficients is satisfactorily explained by using σ^o constants as shown in Fig. 5 ($r = 0.983$; $s = 0.020$).

Fig. 4. The Yukawa-Tsuno plot (numbered as in Table 4).

Reaction dependence on H_0 function would show whether a water molecule was present in the activated complex or not. Although the Zucker-Hammett plot (Fig. 1) is fairly linear, the nonintegral value, -1.7 , for the slope suggests the involvement of water molecule in the rate-determining step²². Bunnett¹¹ has proposed that, for most acid catalysed reactions, plots of $\log k + H_0$ versus $\log a_{H_2O}$ are

Fig. 5. The Yukawa-Tsuno plot (*para*-substituents only) (numbered as in Table 4).

linear or approximately so. In the present investigation, the plot of $\log k + H_0$ versus $\log a_{H_2O}$ (Fig. 6) is reasonably linear with a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.969$ ($s = 0.042$). It seems that the transition state has a high demand for water, as a nucleophile in the rate-limiting step.

The observed kinetic behaviours in presence of $HClO_4$ can be explained by a two-pathway mechanism.

Scheme (i) :

where $R = C_6H_5SO_2^-$

Scheme (ii) :

Composite rate law takes the form of eq. (7),

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAB}]}{dt} = k_2 K_1 K [\text{Ph}][\text{CAB}][\text{H}^+] + k_4 K K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}][\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{CAB}] \quad (7)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k' [\text{Ph}][\text{H}^+] + k'' [\text{H}_2\text{O}][\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (8)$$

where $k' = k_2 K_1 K$ and $k'' = k_4 K K_3$

Eq. (8) demands linear relationship between $k_{\text{cal}}/[\text{H}^+]$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$. The plot shows scatter of individual points. In spite of scatter a reasonably good line (Fig. 7) ($r = 0.966$; $s = 0.290$) proves the validity of the above assumptions. Eq. (8) explains the fractional order dependence on [substrate] and, if the first term is insignificant, then the zero order dependence of [substrate] can be described. The variation in order in $[\text{H}^+]$ between one and two also justifies the proposed reaction scheme.

Fig. 6. The Bunnett plot.

Fig. 7. Plot of $k_{\text{cal}}/[\text{HClO}_4]$ versus HClO_4 .

Most likely cause of the failure to obtain straight line $\rho\sigma$ relationship with substituted phenols is that the addition (step 2) and elimination (step 3) rate constants are comparable. Electron-releasing substituents favour equilibrium addition of phenol while electron-withdrawing ones favour the elimination step, since the positive charge is fractured. Electron-withdrawing substituents in the *meta*- and *para*-positions would not facilitate the formation of cationic character and would lead to a small ρ -value.

Bromide ion catalysis can be explained by the formation of an active Br-Cl intermediate. Solvent effects are similar for oxidation of phenacyl bromides by Ce^{IV} in acetic acid and sulphuric acid media²³. The high degree of organisation in the transition state is very much reflected in the high negative entropy values.

All the *ortho*-substituents studied (barring *o-t*-butyl) depress the reactivity of chlorination process. The ratio of rate constants for *ortho*- and *para*-substituted compounds are listed in Table 7. Except *o-t*-butyl phenols, in all other cases the ratio is < 1 . This suggests that in this conversion steric hindrance predominates over anchimeric assistance in the reactivity.

Table 7. Ratio of rate constants of oxidation for the *ortho*- and *para*-substituted phenols at 313 K

Substituent	$k_{\text{ortho}} \times 10^4$ s^{-1}	$k_{\text{para}} \times 10^4$ s^{-1}	$k_{\text{ortho}}/k_{\text{para}}$
CH_3	1.99	3.03	0.66
<i>t</i> -Butyl	3.60	2.04	1.76
Cl	1.37	1.85	0.74
Br	1.54	1.76	0.88
COOH	1.28	2.25	0.57
NO_2	1.13	1.70	0.66

To understand the composition of localised (L), delocalised (D) and steric effects (S) operating in these reactions, the rate data are analysed with LD and LDS equations^{24,25} (A and B) at 40°.

$$\log k_{\text{ortho}} = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_R + h \quad (A)$$

$$\log k_{\text{ortho}} = -0.388\sigma_1 - 0.241\sigma_R - 3.685$$

(*o-t*-butyl, *o*-CHO and *o*-COOCH₃ excluded in the correlation)

$$(R = 0.932; SE = 0.060; n = 7)$$

$$\log k_{\text{ortho}} = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_R + Sv + h \quad (B)$$

$$\log k_{\text{ortho}} = -0.282\sigma_1 - 0.144\sigma_R - 0.090v - 3.644$$

(assuming planar conformation for -COOH and -NO₂ groups)

$$(R = 0.955; SE = 0.056; n = 7)$$

$$\log k_{\text{ortho}} = -0.313\sigma_1 - 0.266\sigma_R - 0.213v - 3.624$$

(assuming orthogonal conformation for -COOH and -NO₂ groups)

$$(R = 0.980; SE = 0.036; n = 7)$$

Although electrical effects are predominant, small but significant steric effects are observed in the reaction.

The order in the [substrate] depends on the nature of the substrate in the bromination of substituted phenols¹⁵ by *N*-bromosuccinimide. In the present investigation the order dependence on the [substrate] is neither due to the nature of the substituent nor its position. The observed kinetic behaviour may be attributed either to the composite influence of the two parameters or to the concentration effect. This aspect is to be probed further and currently is under investigation.

Experimental

Pure chlorine gas was bubbled through a solution of benzenesulphonamide in 4 *M* sodium hydroxide solution over a period of 1h at 70°. *N*-Chlorobenzenesulphonamide obtained was dried and recrystallised from water. The dichloramine-B contaminant if any, was removed by washing with carbon tetrachloride. Phenols are recrystallised/distilled before use. Acetic acid purification procedure followed was essentially similar to that of Weissberger²⁶.

Experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping the concentration of phenol always in excess. The reaction mixture was homogeneous throughout the course of the reaction. Reactions were followed iodometrically. The pseudo-first order rate coefficients are evaluated from the slopes of the linear plots of log titre versus time by the method of least squares. The rate constants determined were average of two or more determinations. Blank experiments were carried out to determine the decomposition rate of oxidant under the prevailing experimental conditions.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The amount of chlorophenol formed corresponds to the amount of CAB consumed which gives a stoichiometry of 1 : 1 for the reaction between phenol and CAB.

The chlorophenol was extracted with ether, and after the removal of most of the ether, the product was methylated with methyl sulphate and alkali. The product was made acidic and extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was dried and fractionated giving mixed chloroanisoles (b.p. 198–201°)⁶. The product chlorophenol was identified as chlorinated anisoles.

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